

Correction: Hypertension as predictive factor for bevacizumab-containing first-line therapy in metastatic breast and colorectal cancer in BRECOL (GEICAM/2011-04) study

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In this article the ‘Authors’ contributions’ statement was incorrectly given as ‘ARL, JG and JdH: Conception and design, provision of study material or patients, collection

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and/or assembly of data, financial support, data analysis and interpretation, manuscript writing and final approval of manuscript. PGA, BM, RM, LC, PSR, AA, JIC, EC, JP, AS, MV, MRD, VA, JA, SE, LL and LR: provision of study material or patients, collection and/or assembly of data and final approval of manuscript. MJE, RC and SB: data analysis and interpretation, manuscript writing and final approval of manuscript' but should have been 'ARL, JG and JdH: Conception and design, provision of study material or patients, collection and/or assembly of data, financial support, data analysis and interpretation, manuscript writing and final approval of manuscript. PGA, BM, RM, LC, PSR, AA, JIC, EC, JP, AS, MV, MRD, VA, JA, SE, LR, MVG and TM: provision of study material or patients, collection and/or assembly of data and final approval of manuscript. MJE, RC and SB: data analysis and interpretation, manuscript writing and final approval of manuscript.'

The original article has been corrected.

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